

Introducing SafeNcy into the cockpit

Initial draft of proposed additions to the Aircraft Operating Manual
and to the Flight crew SOPs

Aircraft Systems

46 - INFORMATION SYSTEMS

46-xx SAFENCY SYSTEM

Overview

The flight crew uses the SafeNcy System for two purposes:

1. In normal flight, enhance the flight crew situation awareness by providing real time information about reachable landing sites + aeronautical weather data. The flight crew gains a clearer idea of the operational options available if a diversion is necessary.
2. When an emergency occurs, assist the flight crew by proposing immediately a diversion towards the best reachable landing site. The decision whether to follow the SafeNcy diversion proposal remains with the Commander of the flight.

Architecture

The SafeNcy System is supported by the aircraft EFB or directly implemented in the aircraft Flight Management System. It needs a dedicated display with touchscreen function.

The main component of the SafeNcy System is the landing site database that contains all landing sites adapted to the type of aircraft, the intended flight and the type of emergency.

The landing site static data of the database is aggregated under the responsibility of the operator and uploaded in the aircraft system/EFB before the intended flight. Dynamic data (Weather, Notam...) are added and sent in real time to the aircraft to allow pilots to make decisions based on reliable information. An indicator (green light or timestamp) allows to verify the effectiveness of the update in real time.

As the flight progresses, the landing sites proposed by SafeNcy evolve according to the position of the aircraft, the possible range and the type of emergency.

At any time the flight crew has access to a menu with 3 main choices:

1. Landing site information
2. Emergency type
3. Diversion validation/activation

“**Landing site information**” allows to get static and dynamic information about a landing site proposed on the SafeNcy display.

“**Emergency type**” allows the flight crew to characterize a type of emergency/failure. SafeNcy will then propose the closest relevant landing site. Approval by the flight crew activates the SafeNcy trajectory generator which elaborates the best 4D trajectory to reach this landing site. The trajectory generator takes in account the actual aircraft’s technical condition and the resulting performances. This 4D trajectory avoids terrain and dangerous weather.

The SafeNcy algorithms include safety margins for each performance parameter (range, descent angle, remaining energy, landing performance, etc.) since real life often differs from theoretical expectations.

“**Diversion validation/activation**” allows the flight crew to transfer the SafeNcy diversion proposal into the aircraft Flight Guidance System. The workload of the flight crew is relieved by the use of the Flight Directors, Autopilot and the Navigation Modes of the aircraft.

During the diversion, SafeNcy continues to update the situation and can provide an alternative landing site proposal if necessary.

Landing sites classification

The SafeNcy landing site database includes all the possible landing stripes reachable along the route filled in the operational flight plan. The data come from official state aeronautical information providers but also from all available and reliable geographical information systems.

Depending on the type of emergency and the landing sites that can be reached, SafeNcy will always propose the landing site with the longest runway and the best assistance first. To facilitate this sorting, the landing sites are divided into 6 classes.

1. Class 1 : Airport

An airport that the airline could use as a commercial Destination or normal Destination Alternate.

Static criteria:

- At least one runway > 2200m (example based on A320 type aircraft, different value for smaller or bigger aircraft)
- Included in the aircraft NAVDATABASE
- IFR approach procedure with at least CAT 1 (200ft AAL) minima or lower
- ATC services
- Fire assistance (if possible, aircraft category)
- Security OK
- Passenger accommodation

Dynamic criteria:

- Open with ancillary services available (e.g. runway lights at nighttime)
- Real time landing performance fulfilled (taking in account runway surface condition and wind)
- Notam OK
- Weather above minima

2. Class 2 : Airport

An airport that the airline would use only as an en-route alternate if no Class 1 is available.

Static criteria:

- At least one runway > 2000m (example based on A320 type aircraft)
- Not necessarily included in the aircraft NAVDATABASE
- At least an IFR NPA approach procedure (Non Precision Approach)
- At least remote ATC or traffic information.
- At least wind, visibility and QNH available

Dynamic criteria:

- Open
- Real time landing performance fulfilled
- Notam OK
- Approach criteria fulfilled (weather above minima, lights at night,..)

3. Class 3 : Aerodrome

Not necessarily a commercial airport but a usable runway or ex runway or a concrete strip long enough. Typically military airport or former airport no longer in use, or general aviation airfield with a concrete runway.

Static criteria:

- At least one (concrete) runway long enough for an emergency landing with less than the required margin
- Not in the aircraft NAVDATABASE
- No IFR approach procedure
- At least remote ATC

Dynamic criteria:

- Not obstructed
- landing distance with no margin fulfilled
- Pseudo METAR indicating suitable weather

Note: for class 1, 2 or 3, if one or more criteria are not fulfilled the airport could still be presented to the pilot but with an alert providing information about the missing criteria.

4. Class 4 : Airfield

A small general aviation aerodrome with a grass runway or a concrete runway but too short for an emergency landing, allowing nevertheless for a safer touchdown and roll out than Class 5 or 6.

Static criteria:

- At least one runway with no solid obstacle 1000m (TBD) after the touchdown area
- Not in the aircraft NAVDATABASE
- No IFR approach procedure

Dynamic criteria:

- Not obstructed
- Pseudo METAR available for wind (landing direction) and QNH

5. Class 5 : Ditching

An open water area with no obstacles.

Static criteria:

- Open sea or river
- as close as possible to rescue facilities
- ditching areas to be used during initial climb out or approach to an airport should be present in the SafeNcy database.

Dynamic criteria:

- Water temperature
- Wave height
- Pseudo METAR available for wind (landing direction) and QNH

6. Class 6 : Forced landing (off airport but on land)

The best remaining landing site when no Class 1 to 5 is reachable.

Static criteria:

- More or less flat area with no obstacle (natural or artificial)
- One direction identified as providing the longest landing strip.
- as close as possible to rescue facilities
- forced landing areas to be used during initial climb out or approach to an airport should be present in the SafeNcy database.

Dynamic criteria:

- Pseudo METAR available for wind (landing direction) and QNH

Selecting the type of Emergency/Failure

On its own, SafeNcy is not able to identify and categorize the type of emergency/failure the aircraft is undergoing. It is the flight crew's responsibility to call a menu on the SafeNcy display screen to characterize the type of emergency/failure they undergo and the resulting aircraft status (e.g., aircraft fully maneuverable or not).

The Flight crew can choose between five types of emergencies/failures:

1. Type 1: TEFO (Total Engine Flame Out).

The aircraft behaves like a glider. In this type of emergency, the area where to find a landing site is limited in distance and can lead to an off-airport landing. SafeNcy displays the best landing site (based on the proposed classification) in the reachable area.

2. Type 2: ASAP (As Soon As Possible).

This situation is indicated to the pilots as part of an emergency or abnormal checklist. It is defined in the Airbus FCOM as “land as soon as possible at the nearest airport at which a safe landing can be made”. It means that the situation is time-critical but that the pilot should still avoid an off-airport landing. SafeNcy should display the closest, in time, class 1 to 4 aerodrome.

3. Type 3: ANSA (At the Nearest Suitable Airport).

This situation is indicated to the pilots as part of an abnormal checklist. It is defined in the Airbus FCOM as “consider landing at the nearest suitable airport”. There is a note reading: “the suitability criteria should be defined in accordance with the Operator’s policy”. We suggest that SafeNcy displays the closest, in time, class 1 to 3 airport. (It could also be limited to Class 1 to 2).

4. Type 4: FIRE SMOKE/FUMES,

An uncontrolled event can lead to a total loss of the aircraft in few minutes (e.g. uncontrolled fire on board, smoke, fumes, etc.). In this type of emergency, the area where to find a landing site is limited in time (not more than 25 minutes recommended) and can lead to an off airport landing. SafeNcy should display the best landing site (in accordance with the proposed classification) in the reachable area.

5. Type 5: EMER DESCENT due to loss of pressurization.

The Flight crew uses the ASAP or ANSA landing site proposed by SafeNcy but the vertical profile of the 4D trajectory is specific as it must comply with the manufacturer's SOPs regarding available Oxygen reserves and minimum safe altitudes.

This selection menu also allows the flight crew to specify if the aircraft is still fully maneuverable and if the final approach will be IFR or Visual.

How to

1. HOW TO GET SITUATION AWARENESS DURING NORMAL FLIGHT.

The Flight crew calls the SafeNcy display screen.

SafeNcy shows a chart centered on the actual aircraft position. Zoom in and zoom out is available.

Only a short number of landing sites are displayed around the aircraft position. A color code indicates for which type of emergency they fit.

- In cruise, SafeNcy displays:
 - the closest in time TEFO class 1 to 3 airport (if there is one reachable) +
 - the closest (*or the two closest?*) ASAP (Class 1 to 3) airport +
 - the closest (*or the two closest?*) ANSA (class 1 to 2) airport.

Note 1: in normal cruise SafeNcy only displays an off-airport landing if requested by the flight crew via the emergency menu.

Note 2: if, for instance, a Class 1 airport is close and obviously fits for all type of emergencies, the display will be limited to it.

- During the take-off and approach phases, as long as no TEFO airport is reachable, (*generally below 10000ft*) SafeNcy displays 1 or 2 off-airport landing sites allowing the flight crew to make a decision very quickly.

The flight crew can use the SafeNcy menu to :

- 1- select a landing site proposed by SafeNcy by touching it on the screen, operational information will then pop-up:
 - Landing runway/ direction
 - Landing distance available
 - Time to get there and fuel consumption
 - TBD
 - ...
- 2- at any time, simulate an emergency/failure. Completing the Emergency/Failure menu will cause SafeNcy to display the landing site considered best for the simulated emergency and the 4D trajectory to reach it. The flight crew can validate the proposal or select another landing site.

SafeNcy displays the 4D trajectory (lateral and vertical profile) and gives information about the remaining distance and the time to destination.

- 3- verify the presence of the diversion activation button which would allow the transfer of the trajectory into the Flight Guidance System.

2. HOW TO USE SAFENCY WHEN AN EMERGENCY OCCURS.

The Flight crew calls the SafeNcy display screen, followed by the SafeNcy Menu.

The flight crew selects the SafeNcy emergency type (1 to 5), the aircraft status (fully maneuverable or not) and the type of approach (IFR or not) .

SafeNcy proposes the landing site considered as the best for the situation and the 4D trajectory to join it.

The Flight crew validates (or points another landing site on the SafeNcy display).

If the Flight crew is satisfied, they can entrust the trajectory to the flight guidance system of the aircraft.

The Flight crew monitors how the diversion unfolds and is ready to take over if things don't go as planned.

At any time, the Flight crew can ask SafeNcy to provide another option by changing the type of emergency or choosing another landing site.

During the diversion SafeNcy continues to update the remaining energy and can alert the Flight crew if the intended landing site is no longer reachable.

Standard Operating Procedures

Foreword

SafeNcy system is not a MEL item. Dispatch is allowed with SafeNcy inoperative.

In accordance with the airline policy, if SafeNcy is operational, the flight crew shall consider its proposals and eventually challenge them.

The flight crew must report:

- any obviously valid landing site which is not proposed by SafeNcy or missing in its database.
- any landing site proposed by SafeNcy which is obviously not correctly classified or not safe.

FLIGHT PREPARATION

SAFENCY LANDING SITES DATABASE CHECK

The flight crew must check that the SafeNcy landing sites database:

- *Is relevant for the aircraft type*
- *includes the area relevant for the intended flight*
- *is up to date.*

BEFORE TAKE-OFF

SAFENCY DISPLAY SCREEN CHECK

Approaching the takeoff runway threshold, the Flight crew must check that SafeNcy displays landing sites proposals relevant for the intended departure path (SID).

IN FLIGHT (no emergency in progress)

SAFENCY DISPLAY SCREEN MONITOR

Regularly or at least every 15 min, the Flight crew should verify:

- *the ASAP and ANSA landing sites proposed by SafeNcy in order to maintain a good situation awareness.*
- *that the dynamic data is updated in real time.*

CONTEXTUAL BRIEFINGS

Any Flight crew operational briefing should include an assessment of the SafeNcy proposals.

BEFORE APPROACH

SAFENCY DISPLAY SCREEN CHECK

Passing FL100, the Flight crew must check that SafeNcy displays landing sites proposals relevant for the intended arrival (STAR).

ABNORMAL AND EMERGENCY PROCEDURES

Foreword

Golden rules reminder (including SafeNcy):

- Fly, navigate and communicate
- Use the appropriate level of automation at all times
- Understand the FMA (**and SafeNcy**) at all times
- Take action if things do not go as expected.

WHEN AN EMERGENCY OCCURS

Once aircraft under control:

SAFENCY EMERGENCY SELECTION MENUDISPLAY

The PNF calls the SafeNcy Menu allowing to select the type and characteristics of the emergency.

TYPE OF EMERGENCYSELECT

LANDING SITE PROPOSED BY SAFENCY VALIDATE OR CHALLENGE

The flight crew considers the landing site proposed by SafeNcy and decides to select it or select another proposal.

LANDING SITE.....SELECT

As soon as the landing site has been selected, SafeNcy calculates and displays a safe 4D trajectory to join the landing site.

PROPOSED 4D TRAJECTORY VERIFY/VALIDATE

TRANSFER INTO FGS EXECUTE

Once the emergency diversion trajectory is approved by the flight crew, it can be transferred from SafeNcy into the aircraft Flight Guidance System.

APPROPRIATE LEVEL OF AUTOMATION USE

If possible, Flight Director and Auto pilot should be used to lower the flight crew workload.

DIVERSION TO LANDING SITE..... MONITOR

The Flight crew must continuously evaluate the remaining energy and verify that a safe landing at the selected landing site remains possible. If the situation worsens a new SafeNcy landing site must be requested (via the emergency menu).